

Integrated germplasm improvement—flood-prone

IR4630-derived lines are stable high yielders under saline conditions in Kerala, India

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IR4630-22-2-17 was used in a rice breeding program to develop high-yielding, saline-tolerant varieties for pokkali cultivation. Three medium-duration, tall lines were evaluated with popular pokkali varieties, Vyttila 1 and Vyttila 3, for grain yield and other agronomic attributes.

The experiment was laid out in 50-m² plots in a randomized block design with four replications during 1988-91 dry season. Sowing dates and field salinity differed across years, depending on rainfall availability. Grain yield was recorded at 14% moisture level. Genotype stability over four environments was analyzed.

Regression of genotypes for average yield on the environmental index resulted in regression coefficients (*b*) from 0.805 to 1.191. The variance due to deviations

from regression (*s*²*d*) ranged from -0.805 to -0.296 (Table 1). These stability parameters were not significant, indicating all lines tested were stable yielders across the environments.

Table 1. Mean grain yield (t/ha) and estimates of stability parameters for 5 rice genotypes over 4 environments. Kerala, India. 1988-91.

Genotype	$\bar{X}$	<i>b</i>	<i>s</i> ² <i>d</i>
KAU904	3.3	1.028	-0.805
KAU905	3.7	0.805	-0.612
KAU906	3.7	0.990	-0.296
Vyttila 1	2.8	0.991	-0.585
Vyttila 3	3.0	0.191	-0.689
Av	3.3		

Rice culture KAU906 had *b* value close to unity (0.990), indicating its highly stable performance across the environments tested. This culture yielded the most (3.7 t/ha) and was released recently in Kerala as Vyttila 4 for cultivation in pokkali areas. (See Table 2 for morphoagronomic attributes.)

The three genotypes derived from the IR4630 cross were stable yielders over time. They are recommended for use in breeding programs aimed at developing saline-tolerant cultivars with high yield potential and adaptability. ■

Table 2. Morphoagronomic attributes of saline-tolerant rice genotypes from Vyttila, India.

Genotype	Parentage	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Fertile grains/panicle (no.)	Sterility (%)
KAU904	Chettivirippu/IR4630-22-2-17	120	164	14	151	125	17.2
KAU905	Chettivirippu/IR4630-22-2-17	120	162	13	125	108	14.0
KAU906	Chettivirippu/IR4630-22-2-17	120	161	14	140	129	7.9
Vyttila 1	Choottupokkali (sel)	115	158	13	128	112	12.5
Vyttila 3	Vyttila 1/TN1	115	161	15	134	125	6.7

Crop and resource management

Fertilizer management—inorganic

Increasing efficiency of nitrogen in rice through split application

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We investigated the effect of applying 124 kg N/ha on Basmati 385 in two, three, and four splits during 1990-92 dry seasons in farmers' fields in Punjab, Pakistan. Phosphorus, K, and Zn were applied to all treatments at 35, 67, and 5

kg/ha, respectively. The soils were clay loam with pH of 8.1-8.4, EC of 1.7-3.4 dS/m, Olsen's P of 4-8 mg/kg, 0.48-0.76%

organic matter, and 160-212 mg/kg ammonium acetate extractable K. Thirty-day-old rice seedlings were transplanted

Table 1. Schedule of application of N (kg/ha) in farmers' fields, Punjab, Pakistan. 1990-92 dry seasons.

Treatment (no.)	Last puddling	20-25 DAT ^a	40-45 DAT	60-65 DAT
1	0	0	0	0
2	62	0	62	0
3	41	41	41	0
4	31	31	31	31

^aDAT = days after transplanting.